

Center for Composite Materials

Characterization and Modeling of Deformation Mechanisms of Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Prepreg during Thermoforming

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TuFF: Tailored universal Feedstock for Forming

- **Chopped fibers are aligned** by water flow onto a film
- Films of aligned fiber are prepregged with resin
- Prepreg can be used in **thermoforming process**
 - **Allows for stretch** during forming
 - Final properties comparable to continuous UD prepreg

Role of Numerical Model

- **Goal:** Develop tool to:
 - Guide geometry and process conditions to minimize failed parts.
 - Maximize manufacturing rate.
- **Modeling optimizes process** without spending material, energy, labor.
- **Develop and validate** model's prediction of **deformation**

Model Development Framework

Model Development Framework

Example, Longitudinal Extension:

Axial Extension Experiments: Setup and Data Measurement

- **Axial extension tests** characterize TuFF in a primary deformation mechanism
- Goal:
 - **Measure** strain + stress as a function of strain rate + temperature
- Procedure:
 - Stretch a 25.4×90 mm sample at known strain rates (s^{-1}) and temperatures ($^{\circ}C$)
 - Extension at constant strain rate

Test setup: a sample is gripped and stretched inside an environment chamber

Data analysis: Digital image correlation (DIC) tracks local strains over time.

Force is measured by a load cell to calculate stress (not shown)

Model Development Framework

Example, Longitudinal Extension:

Axial Extension Simulation: Constitutive Equation and Acquiring Inputs

- Developed a model that **matches uniaxial extension data**
- Constitutive equation:
 - Viscous equation with strain softening component

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \eta_P \cdot \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} C_{11} & C_{12} & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{11} \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{22} \\ \dot{\gamma}_{12} \end{bmatrix}$$

Stresses = Polymer viscosity · Directional magnification from fibers · Strain rates

$$D_{11} = C \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon_{11}}{D}\right) + (1.0 - C) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon_{11}}{F}\right)$$

Strain softening = First phase [peak] + Second phase [long-term]

Stress-strain behavior of one TuFF ply:
experimental data.
($\dot{\epsilon} = 0.001 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $T = 40^\circ \text{C}$)

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Stress-strain behavior of one TuFF ply:
comparison between experiment and simulation
($\dot{\epsilon} = 0.001 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $T = 40^\circ \text{C}$)

Axial Extension Simulation: Validation of Model

Local strain over time of
DIC capture (left) and
simulation (right)

Stress-strain behavior of one TuFF ply:
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($\dot{\epsilon} = 0.001 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $T = 40^\circ \text{C}$)

Model Development Framework

Example, Longitudinal Extension:

Forming Characterization System

Equipment developed and acquired under
ONR Grant No. N00014-22-1-2124

Forming
Characterization
System
Interlaken SP75

GOM ARAMIS
12MP DIC

Plane Strain Gas Bulge Tool Set

Open-Mold Bead Simulation

Bulge die used in experiments.

- **Matching conditions of experiment:**
 - Layup: $[0/90]_5$ TuFF with single bladder membrane.
 - Inputs from 40°C , $\dot{\epsilon} = 0.001 \text{ s}^{-1}$ test.
 - Gas pressure: 0.8 kPa/s ramp for 250 seconds.
 - Boundary condition: clamped around bead for no slip-in.
- **Strain and strain rate over time** are tracked at center of outermost ply.

Obtaining Gas Pressure Profile

- Forming window suggests process conditions
 - Strain Rate + Temperature

Gas Pressure vs. Time

Strain Rate vs. Time

Stress vs. Time

TuFF needs range of stress to stretch

Model Development Framework

Example, Longitudinal Extension:

Accuracy of Forming Model

Conditions

- Temp = 40°C
- Pressure = 0.8 kPa/s ramp for 250 seconds.
- Layup = $[0/90]_S$ with single diaphragm
- Interfaces have Coulomb friction, $\mu = 0.4$

Contour showing strain in X-dir at t = 200s.

Development of strain over time.

Development of bulge height over time.

Conclusions

Extensional properties predicts stretch in forming

- Validated model to predict longitudinal extensor in forming.
- Simple equation + properties works:

Longitudinal Extension:

- Constant strain rate, impulsively started
- Single ply
- No transverse pressure

Forming:

- Gas pressure-driven
- Multi-ply with bladder
- Transverse pressure

- Suggests continuum-scale viscosity behaves in the same manner for single ply extension and multi-ply blanks in bead forming

Questions?
